

Genomic Eye Color Classification with Machine Learning

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Abstract

We performed eye color classification with machine learning on sequenced genomes from the Harvard Personal Genome Project using support vector classifiers on 78 genomes that were tiled by Curoverse. The classifier consistently predicted eye color to 95% accuracy. From the coefficients of the classifier, we were then able to locate rs12913832, a SNP in the OCA2/HERC2 region responsible for producing the blue eye color, and we proved this located gene is consistent with previous literature.

1 Introduction

When working with sequenced genomes, output genomes can often be as large as tens of gigabytes, and as a result variant calling and computational projects become inefficient and slow. With the open-source Arvados Lightning Project, a genome is able to be compacted down significantly from its raw format into "tiles," an array of integers containing references to a tile library containing different base pair variants. This series of integers creates convenient input into machine learning algorithms, allowing classification projects to be run in minutes, rather than hours or days. Both the tiling process and this project are kept open-source, and the open-source nature of these projects allows for future researchers with less specialized knowledge to apply machine learning to sequenced genomes.

1.1 Arvados Lightning Project and Harvard PGP

The Arvados Lightning Project [Guthrie et al. (2015)] is designed to compact genomes from their raw (GFF, GVCF) format to a new representation allowing for simple and consistent naming, annotation, queries, machine learning, and clinical screening. Using Lightning, the genomes are "tiled"—a technique that divides the genome into about 10 million overlapping, variable-length sequences, or "tiles", each with a unique 24-base tag at each end. This tiling process produces a one dimensional NumPy array of integers representing a specific tile variant at each tile position. The Harvard Personal Genome Project (PGP) curates well-sequenced genomes made public by volunteers willing to share their data, as well as phenotypic data provided in surveys. The PGP allows genomic data to be accessible and easily available for everyone to use. We used the "Basic 2015 Phenotypes" survey, which contains survey responses for left/right eye color and hair color, among other traits.

2 Materials/Methods

2.1 Survey Results

Personal Genome Project participants were asked to provide a brief description of each of their eye colors in the "Basic Phenotypes 2015 Survey." [Ouyang (n.d.)] They were provided with a selection from 24 images and asked which they would most similarly classify their eye color (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: List of eye images that participants were asked to choose from (slightly changed for formatting) [Franssen et al. (2008)]

Figure 2: Responses from all the PGP participants.

From the eye color chart (see Figure 1), groups 1 to 13 were classified as "blue" as they lacked dark pigmenting. From 14 on, the eye colors evidently contained brown pigmenting, therefore were classified as "not blue". There were a total of 78 respondents who also had tiled genomes, and we used these data with their respective genomes as inputs to our classifier. We used the left eye color from survey responses for analysis, but when reproducing the work with the right eye color there were no significant differences in the results. We found 33 "not blue" responses and 45 "blue" responses in the survey. [Fang (2017a)]

Figure 3: The number of participants with the blue eye color versus the number of participants who did not have the blue eye color.

2.2 Support Vector Machines

We used a linear support vector classifier (LinearSVC) in scikit-learn [Pedregosa et al. (2011)] to produce the machine learning algorithm. Due to the transparent nature of this model, we are able to see which specific tile influenced the classifier the most, allowing us to draw further conclusions from the data. We performed a Grid-Search cross validation using scikit-learn to determine the

optimal C penalty parameter, testing on a 10-step logarithmic scale from 1×10^{-2} to 1×10^1 . (See Figure 4) The optimal hyperparameters found included a C penalty parameter of 0.06, balanced class weight, and l1 regularization.

Figure 4: Accuracy versus C value, determined by the Grid-Search Cross Validation

2.3 Categorical Exclusion

The classifier consistently misclassified 9 participants when running leave-one-out validation. 6 of the 9 incorrect classifications had self described their eye color as "hazel." In the entire sample of 78 genomes, we found 17 total responses of hazel, and several participants were unsure about their self-classification, leaving an uncertainty in the data. We therefore performed a categorical exclusion of all participants with hazel eyes and retrained our classifier, achieving an improved accuracy. When we excluded hazel, there were 25 "non-blue" responses and 36 "blue" responses. We will be including results from both of our classifiers.

2.4 Machine Learning & Training

Each tiled genome is represented as a NumPy array of integers; for the Harvard Personal Genome Project dataset, there are 2,469,062 tiles/integers in each genome. While the full tiled genome includes significantly more tiles, low-quality base pairs or "nocalls" found during sequencing are not included in the tile set, and that specific tile is dropped from the rest of the tiled genomes. The 218 high quality tiled genomes are stored in a $218 \times 2,469,062$ NumPy array curover.se/su921-4zz18-xmmmg0qn0wuaxkl. Training and prediction took approximately two minutes in total, but time varies depending on the computational resources available. When the classifier trains, it assigns each index in the genome a coefficient, representing its "weight" in the determining the classification. Because we used l1 regularization during training, the classifier, attempts to reduce as many coefficients to zero as possible to eliminate as many relevant variables as possible.

3 Results

3.1 Summary

Using 10-fold cross validation, our classifier had $84.6 \pm 9.5\%$ accuracy; through leave-one-out CV, the classifier was $88.5\% \pm 31.9\%$ accurate. After we performed the categorical hazel exclusion and retrained the classifier, it was $94.6\% \pm 8.4\%$ accurate with 10-fold CV and $95.1\% \pm 21.5\%$ accurate with leave-one-out CV. The classifier and exact training scripts written are available in Jupyter notebooks in the GitHub repository, and work can be reproduced in Docker containers. [Fang (2017a)]

Figure 5: Leave-one-out cross validation results for classifier trained on all data

Figure 6: Leave-one-out cross validation results for classifier trained on categorically excluded hazel data.

When the hazel responses were included, the classifier found approximately 50 coefficients. The highest weighted coefficient was at index 1,792,420 in the array with weight 0.85 (see Figure 7) Other coefficients were at least one order of magnitude lower than 0.85, so we did not include them in the analysis. When the hazel responses were excluded, the number of coefficients was reduced to just 2, and the same tile (1,792,420) had the highest weight at 0.93.

Figure 7: Coefficients found by the classifier with their respective weights (on a logarithmic scale).

4 Analysis

4.1 Tile Searching

Using an open-source tile searching script, [Fang (2017b)] we located the specific tile at index 1,792,420. The script produced the following output from the index:

Tile information:

Tile Path: 0x288

Tile Step: 0x415

Tile Phase: 0x0

hg19:chr15:0288 99840 132519571 15 16

Base pair location:

0414 28365579

0415 28365804

Variant Difference Indices: [63, 82, 138, 178]

The search determined that the tile was located on path 0288, step 0415, and phase 0, from base pairs 28,365,579 to 28,365,804. According to the NCBI gene database (ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/gene/8924) the HERC2 gene lies on base pairs 28,356,183 to 28,567,313 on the reference genome used by the PGP (GRCh37.p13 genome). [NCBI (2004)] Eiberg, H. et al, found that the HERC2 protein is responsible for coding for the blue eye color, therefore our searching script indicated successful preliminary results. [Eiberg et al. (2008)]

4.2 Tile Variants and SNP

Our tile searching script found that the tile most strongly associated with eye color was at base pair location 28,365,579. Anderson, J. et al, 2016 noted that "the intensity of pigmentation in the iris is strongly associated with one single-nucleotide polymorphism, rs12913832:A>G," and that the SNP rs12913832 is located at the base pair 28,365,618. [Andersen et al. (2016)] Due to the nature of the tiling process, each tile variant begins with a 24-base pair long "tag-set" marking the overlap from the previous tile. [Guthrie et al. (2015)] Therefore, the first 24 base pairs in our tile are an "offset." We used the following calculations to determine the location of rs12913832 on the located tile:

$$\text{base pair location} = \text{SNP base pair location} - \text{tile location} \quad (1)$$

$$= 28,365,618 - 28,365,579 \quad (2)$$

$$= 39 \quad (3)$$

$$\text{SNP location on tile} = \text{offset} + \text{base pair location} \quad (4)$$

$$= 24 + 39 \quad (5)$$

$$= 63 \quad (6)$$

Therefore, rs12913832, the SNP found by Anderson, J. et al, is located at index 63 on the tile. Our own results are consistent with these conclusions: the tile searching script finds four differences among the variants of our tile: [63, 82, 138, 178], and index 63 is the first of these. On rs12913832, the brown eye color is caused by an A>A SNP and A>G SNP, and the blue eye color is caused by a G>G SNP. We mapped these SNP data with survey responses and their respective tile variants at index 63. We performed a Fisher’s exact test to determine statistical significance using the A>G and G>G SNPs (there were not enough responses containing the A>A SNP). Whether or not hazel was excluded from our tests, results were found to be statistically significant at $p < .0001$.

Figure 8: Table used for the Fisher exact test.

5 Conclusion

The combination of the Personal Genome Project’s public genomic data and the Arvados Lightning project allows applications such as machine learning to be run in a significantly shorter time than processing the raw genome. Without any prior knowledge of the genome, we were able to find the HERC2 gene and locate a single SNP in the region that determines eye color. Given more data, with some slight modifications these same algorithms and programs can be extended to detect further genetic traits. We invite all interested users to rerun our analysis. All programs used are open-source on GitHub [Fang (2017a)], in the form of Jupyter Notebooks as well as standalone Python scripts. A Docker image is optionally provided for easy reuse, as well as an Arvados pipeline at

curover.se/su92l-j7d0g-y6owdqvhkjb2y.

References

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